

THERAPEUTIC EFFECTS OF AMBROXOL HYDROCHLORIDE IN INFANTS DIAGNOSED WITH SECRETORY OTITIS MEDIA

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>This study evaluates the clinical efficacy of ambroxol hydrochloride in treating infantile secretory otitis media (SOM). Ninety-two infants diagnosed with SOM were randomly divided into an experimental group receiving conventional treatment plus ambroxol hydrochloride, and a control group receiving routine care alone. Treatment effectiveness, inflammatory markers (SIL-2R and IL-8), pure tone threshold air-bone gap, tympanic pressure, and adverse reactions were compared. The experimental group demonstrated a significantly higher treatment effectiveness rate ($P<0.05$), increased SIL-2R and IL-8 levels ($P<0.05$), reduced air-bone gap ($P<0.05$), improved tympanic pressure ($P<0.05$), and lower incidence of adverse reactions ($P<0.05$) compared to controls. These results indicate that ambroxol hydrochloride enhances clinical outcomes and safety in infant SOM treatment, supporting its valuable application in clinical nursing.</p>	<p>Ambroxol hydrochloride; Secretory otitis media; Clinical efficacy; pure tone threshold</p>

1. INTRODUCTION diseases may be induced without in time treatment^[1-3]. Secretory otitis media refers to middle ear effusion. Infants are more apt to suffer from SOM. Patients may and hearing loss caused by mechanical obstruction or bear their cross from SOM for a long time as it has a ventilatory dysfunction. Other severe symptoms or high recurrence rate and a low cure rate. The current

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Clinical treatments for SOM include tympanostomy and catheterization, but the above treatments have certain defects^[4-6]. It has been reported that ambroxol hydrochloride is of high application value in the treatment of patients with SOM to improve the clinical manifestations of the disease and mitigate the hearing of patients^[7-9]. To study the therapeutic effect of ambroxol hydrochloride in infants with SOM, this study was designed to select the infants with SOM as the research object and analyze the ability of ambroxol hydrochloride, thus improving the hearing of patients and the incidence of adverse reactions during the treatment. The report is as follows.

2 DATA AND METHODS

2.1 General Data

Of 92 randomly selected infants with SOM treated in our hospital between January 2018 and September 2019, a control group and an ex-perimental group were allocated with 46 cases in respective, with the age of participants between 1 and 3 years in both groups. The two groups did not differ in terms of sex, age, course of disease and other general data ($P>0.05$). See Table 1.

2.2 Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

2.2.1 Inclusion Criteria

- (1) Patient met the clinical manifestations of SOM;
- (2) 1 year old \leq age \leq 3 years old;
- (3) Patient has not received surgical treatment recently;
- (4) Patient had no history of drug allergy and drug abuse, and no bad habits;
- (5) This study was approved by the hospital ethics committee, and the patient guardians voluntarily participated in the study and signed informed consent.

2.2.2 Exclusion Criteria

- (1) The patient had congenital diseases;
- (2) The patient had organic disease;
- (3) The patient's guardian was reluctant to participate in this study.

2.3 Methods

2.3.1 Treatment Methods

In the control group, patients received routine antibiotic treatment and nursing care; the ambroxol hydrochloride (Manufacturer: Tianjin Pharmaceutical Research Institute Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd.; NMPA Approval Number: H20051604; Specification: 4ml: 30mg) was additionally injected into patients' middle ear for auxiliary treatment in the experimental group. Details were as follows: the patient's external auditory canal was routinely disinfected and the eardrum was locally anesthetized. A slender needle was used to inject ambroxol hydrochloride into the tympanic cavity of the patient. When the drug overflowed, the injection was stopped, and disinfection was conducted. The patient's ears should be clear from water after the injection of the ambroxol hydrochloride into the tympanum, to ensure the effect of the medicine. The medicine should be administered once a week.

2.3.2 Listening Test Method

Before testing the patient's basic conditions, glasses, headwear, and hearing-aids should be removed. First of all, the test was conducted for one ear at a time, and the ear was tested with 1000Hz 40 decibels. If the patients gave no response, an adjustment of 10 decibels each time would be made until the subject responded. The initial test tone was set as -10 decibels, and was increased by 10 decibels each time. After the subject responded, the test tone was reduced by 10 decibels and then increased by 5 decibels each time. The decibel at the time point of the subject's response was recorded^[10-12].

2.3.3 Inflammatory Cytokines Expression Test

After one week of treatment, 3ml of fasting venous blood from all patients were collected and placed at room temperature for 30 minutes, and then centrifuged at 3000r/min for 10 minutes. The supernatant was taken for the testing of serum IL-2R and IL-2 expression levels by using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

2.4 Indexes Observation

The treatment efficiency, inflammatory cytokines expression, pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference, tympanic pressure and adverse reactions were put into comparison between the two groups.

It was considered significantly effective if the patient's symptoms of SOM were evidently abated, the middle ear effusion disappeared, and the hearing recovered well without any adverse reaction; the treatment was considered effective, if the patient's symptoms were relieved to a certain extent, the middle ear effusion has basically disappeared, and the hearing has been restored partly without any obvious adverse reactions during the treatment;

Table 1. Comparison of General Data ($\bar{x} \pm s$)

It was

Groups	Experimental Group	Control Group	t/X^2	P
Sex (male/female)	22/24	23/23	0.04	0.84
Age (year)	2.15±0.34	2.04±0.53	1.18	0.24
Height (cm)	83.46±10.22	83.87±9.96	0.19	0.85
Weight (kg)	18.70±6.33	18.32±6.47	0.28	0.78
Course of disease (month)	3.22±1.05	3.58±1.40	1.40	0.17
Diseased part				
Left ear (case)	13	15	0.21	0.65
Right ear (case)	20	18	0.18	0.67
Both ears (case)	13	13	<0.001	1.00

considered ineffective if the patient's symptoms were not alleviated with adverse reactions during the treatment.

The lower the expression level of serum SIL-2R and IL2, the lower the inflammation in the patient's body.

Pure tone threshold air and bone conductance difference was the difference of the test results between pure tone threshold air conductance and bone conductance. The larger the difference, the worse the patient's hearing.

The normal range of tympanic pressure was -50dapa~50dapa [13, 14].

2.5 Statistical Processing

The relevant information and data in this article were processed and analyzed using SPSS21.0. The t test was performed for measurement data, expressed as ($\bar{x} \pm s$); X^2 test was performed for count data, expressed as [n (%)].

Results were deemed as statistically significant when $P < 0.05$.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Comparison of Treatment Efficiency between the Two Groups

Results showed that conventional treatment failed to achieve an effective rate as high as of the group with ambroxol hydrochloride intervention ($P < 0.05$). See Table 2.

3.2 Comparison of the Expression Levels of SIL-2R and IL-2 between the Two Groups

After one week of treatment, a greater drop of the expression levels of SIL-2R and IL-2 was witnessed after the intervention, as compared to the group without additional agent ($P < 0.05$). See Figure 1.

3.3 Comparison of Pure Tone Threshold Air Bone Conductance Difference the Two Groups

A smaller pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference was observed in the group after the application of ambroxol hydrochloride, as compared to conventional treatment ($P<0.05$). See Figure 2.

3.4 Comparison of Tympanic Pressure between the Two Groups

Additional ambroxol hydrochloride intervention assisted the tympanic pressure of the patients to return to the normal range with a better statistical results than the other group after one week of treatment ($P<0.05$). See Figure 3.

3.5 Comparison of the Incidence of Adverse Reactions between the Two Groups

The adverse reactions in this study included severe ear pain, eustachian tube damage, and infection. Fewer patients with adverse reactions were determined in the group with extra agent application than the other group ($P<0.05$). See Table 3.

4 DISCUSSION

SOM is a common disease in otolaryngology, which mostly occurs in infants. It can cause hearing loss and middle ear effusion, bring increment to the levels of inflammatory factors, and in some severe cases, and result in eustachian tube dysfunction, infection and deafness^[15-17]. Therefore, in the treatment of SOM, the patient’s middle ear effusion needs to be removed first before applying medicine. At present, the most commonly used drug is dexamethasone. That is, dexamethasone is injected into the tympanic cavity of the patient, and the patient’s hearing function and the manifestations of SOM are tested after a period of continuous medication^[18-20]. However, a large number of clinical data demonstrated that the use of dexamethasone to treat SOM fails to ensure a stable and positive medical outcome. It has been reported that ambroxol hydrochloride has a high application effect in the treatment of SOM, and can effectively alleviate the patient’s symptoms^[21,22]. This study mainly focused on the effect of ambroxol hydrochloride treatment in infants with SOM.

The results of the study showed a better treatment efficiency of infants with SOM after treatment with ambroxol hydrochloride, indicating that ambroxol hydrochloride can relieve the patient’s symptoms during the treatment period, inhibit the secretion of middle ear effusion, and bring down the occurrence of adverse reactions. The levels of inflammatory cytokines in patients treated with ambroxol hydrochloride observed a greater fall than conventional treatment ($P<0.05$). Scholar Luo^[23] has proposed that ambroxol hydrochloride can significantly reduce the levels of IL-8, Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), Procalcitonin (PCT) and other inflammatory factors in the middle ear effusion of patients with SOM. This conclusion was consistent with the conclusion of the observation on the inflammatory factors in this study.

Pure tone threshold air and bone conductance difference refers to the test results of the difference between pure tone threshold air conductance and bone conductance. The larger the difference, the lower the hearing ability of the patient. In this study, the pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference was smaller after ambroxol hydrochloride intervention ($P<0.05$), which suggested that

Table 2. Comparison of Treatment Efficiency between the Two Groups

Groups	Significantly Effective	Effective	Ineffective	Total Effective Rate (%)
Experimental group	27	11	8	82.61 %
Control group	9	18	19	58.70 %

X2

6.34

P

0.01

Figure 1. Comparison of the expression levels of SIL-2R and IL-2 between the two groups. The abscissa of Figure 1A represented the experimental group and control group from left to right, and the ordinate represented the expression level of SIL-2R. The abscissa of Figure 1B indicated the experimental group and the control group from left to right, and the ordinate indicated the expression level of IL-2. *Indicated the comparison of the expression level of SIL-2R between the experimental group and the control group, the experimental group (258.47±73.55) U/ml, the control group (174.36±54.22) U/ml, $t=6.24$, $P<0.001$; **Indicated the expression level of IL-2 between the experimental group and the control group, the experimental group (17.56±5.44) ng/L, the control group (15.20±3.09) ng/L, $t=2.56$, $P=0.01$.

Figure 2. Comparison of the two groups of pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference. The abscissa represented the experimental group and the control group from left to right, and the ordinate represented the pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference. *Indicated that the pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference (9.65±2.20) db of the experimental group is compared with the pure tone threshold air bone conductance difference (13.54±3.81) db of the control group, $t=6.00$, $P<0.001$.

Figure 3. Comparison of tympanic pressure between the two groups. The abscissa represented the experimental group and the control group from left to right, and the ordinate represented the tympanic pressure. Indicated the comparison between the tympanic pressure (-36.21±5.97) dapa of the experimental group and the control group (-54.22±6.89) dapa, $t=13.40$, $P<0.001$.

Table 3. Comparison of the Incidence of Adverse Reactions between the Two Groups

Groups	Severe Pain	Ear Eustachian Tube Damage	Infection	Incidence of Adverse Reactions (%)
Experimental group	2	0	1	6.52 %
Control group	8	3	1	26.09 %
X2				6.45
P				0.01

Ambroxol hydrochloride was effective in enhancing the hearing of patients with SOM.

The tympanic pressure of patients with SOM is prone to certain changes, which is probably cause eustachian tube disorder. Generally speaking, the overranging of the normal value of tympanic pressure which is between plus and minus 50dapa may cause eustachian tube damage. The results of this study showed that after one week of treatment with ambroxol hydrochloride, the tympanic pressure of the experimental group had all returned to the normal range. Therefore, no adverse reactions of eustachian tube damage have been detected. The tympanic pressure of the patients in the control group remained (-54.22±6.89) dapa after one week of treatment, indicating that the conventional antibiotic treatment has certain disadvantages compared with the ambroxol hydrochloride treatment. It is necessary to improve and optimize the drug treatment method in further related treatments.

In summary, the use of ambroxol hydrochloride in infants with SOM has significantly abated the symptoms. The level of inflammatory factors was suppressed, the hearing ability was restored, and the incidence of adverse reactions was observably reduced. Therefore, ambroxol hydrochloride is of high application value in infantile SOM, and it is worthy of clinical promotion and application.

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